

Study of the Characteristics of the Measuring Circuit of the Silicon Integrated Mechanical Magnitude Transducer at Temperatures above +100°C

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Published in 1984: [Tikhomirov, M. Y. (1984). Study of the characteristics of the measuring circuit of the silicon integrated mechanical magnitude transducer at temperatures above +100°C. Works of the Moscow Forestry Engineering Institute., 158, 53.].

Abstract

The results of experimental studies on the characteristics of bridge measuring circuits of integrated transducers with ion-alloyed and diffusion piezoresistors in the temperature range of +20°C to 280°C are reviewed.

The effect of p-n junction isolating piezoresistors of integral mechanical transducers from the shunt action of the elastic element on the metrological characteristics of sensors at temperatures above 100°C is not sufficiently covered in the technical literature. Estimates of the operating temperature range vary significantly and therefore require clarification. This paper presents the results of experimental studies on the characteristics of bridge measuring circuits (MC) with ion-alloyed and diffusion piezoresistors in the temperature range of +20°C to +180°C.

The quality of piezoresistor isolation from the silicon elastic element (EE) is characterized by a branch of the inversely shifted p-n junction volt-ampere characteristic (CVC). The inversely shifted CVC is determined by the doping level of carriers in the bulk charge region and the region bounded by the diffusion length from the p-n junction boundary of resistors to the EE region. It can be considered that

$$I_{\text{rev}} = I_{0\text{gen}} + I_{\text{Sgen}} + I_d, \quad (1)$$

where $I_{0\text{gen}}$ is the carrier generation current in the carrier-poor p-n junction region in the body of the elastic element; I_{Sgen} is the carrier generation current in the carrier-poor p-n junction region on the surface of the elastic element; I_d is the diffusion component of the reverse current.

Using the results of ¹, the temperature dependence of the inverse current density in the temperature range under study is determined by the relation.

$$J_{\text{rev}}(T) = q \frac{W_{p-n}}{2} \left(\frac{1}{\tau_0} + K_{p-n} \cdot S_0 \right) n_i e^{21.3 \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T} \right)} + q \frac{L_p}{\tau_p N_p} \cdot n_i^2 e^{42.5 \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T} \right)} \quad (2)$$

where n_i - carrier concentrations in intrinsic semiconductors; T_0 - lower temperature limit; W_{p-n} - width of the volume charge region; τ_0, τ_p - carrier lifetime in the volume charge region and in the elastic element, respectively; S_0 - surface recombination velocity; L_p - diffusion length of minority carriers in the elastic element; N_p - impurity concentration in the elastic element; K_{p-n} - perimeter-to-area ratio of the $p-n$ junction.

When deriving the calculated dependence of the reverse current density on temperature $J_{\text{rev}}(T)$, as shown in Figure 1, the temperature dependence $\tau_p(T)$ for the studied silicon was taken into account.

For an idealized structure of an isolating $p-n$ junction, it is assumed that the concentration of ionized atoms, which determine the volume charge region and the associated electric field intensity,

is uniformly distributed in the Y-axis direction, coinciding with the metallurgical boundary of the junction. In real $p - n$ junctions, the concentration of ionized atoms in the corners of rectangular MC elements may increase, which apparently leads to changes in the parameters determining the surface and volume generation components of the reverse current, and thus affects the dependence of $J_{rev}(T)$ on the number of these corners n in the topological structure.

Figure 1: Temperature dependences of reverse current density of p-n junction isolating ion-alloyed and diffusion contact areas of the metasuring circuit: \blacksquare - #1 ; \oplus - #2; \blacktriangle - #4 ; \bullet - #5; \otimes - #7 ; \circ - #10

To investigate the characteristics, experimental samples of IPT (integrated force piezoresistive transducers with beam-shaped EE) were fabricated from n-type silicon crystals with (100) orientation, having a resistivity of $\rho_{ee} = 4.5 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$ and a diffusion length of minority carriers $L_p = 0.01 \text{ cm}$.

Beam-type IPT (force transducers) contain specially designed test MCs with different geometric parameters. Figure 2 shows the investigated topological structures of the MCs and their geometric parameters.

A topological structure of a bridge circuit is chosen, where equal square contact regions with a size of b and centered at the vertices of a square with a size of a , are connected by four single-strip piezoresistive channels of width d_{ch} for both longitudinal and transverse piezoresistors. Such a scheme allows for:

- Approximating the initial transfer coefficient, $K_{mc0}(T)$, to zero and minimizing its temperature dependence.
- Reducing the total area of the isolating p-n junction to values of $A_{p-n} \leq 2 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2$.

Two methods of doping the piezoresistive channels (PCH) of the measurement scheme were implemented during the fabrication of the force IPTs:

1. Ion implantation of boron with a doping dose of $2 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and surface resistance $R_{see} = 85 \Omega/\square$.

Number Structure	MC Structure	Geometric Parameters, $\times 10^{-4}cm$				The number of angles in the p-n junction structure, n	$A_{p-n}, \times 10^{-4}cm^2$	K_{p-n}
		a	b	d_{ch}	b_c			
#1		60	20	10	10	32	0.52	1400
#2		80	40	20	20	32	0.96	833
#4		120	60	20	40	32	1.92	667
#5		140	80	20	60	32	3.04	526
#7		120	40	40	20	8	1.92	500
#10		$R1 = 100$	$R2 = 60$	40	20	-	2.0	500

Figure 2: Topological structures and geometrical parameters of MC on test-IPT force transducer

2. Boron diffusion with average specific resistances of the PCH (where "auto-compensation" of temperature-dependent sensitivity changes^{2 3} can be expected in the range of $(0 \div 300)^\circ C$ when the MC is powered by a stabilized current): $0.02 \Omega \cdot cm$, $0.03 \Omega \cdot cm$, and $0.06 \Omega \cdot cm$.

For all IPT variations, low-resistance contact regions were formed by boron diffusion with surface resistances of $(10 \div 12) \Omega/\square$.

Figure 3: Dependence of insulating p-n junction reverse current density for MS #5: \times - with diffusion PCHs; \circ - with ion-alloyed PCHs.

Figure 3 shows the dependence of the reverse current density of isolating p-n junctions on temperature for ion-implanted and diffusion PCHs in test MC structure #5 with $A_{p-n} = 3 \cdot 10^{-4} cm^2$. The noticeable difference in the change for experimental samples below $+150^\circ C$ can be explained by the influence of the variation in surface recombination velocity S_0 values. The temperature dependence of the diffusion component of the reverse current becomes dominant at temperatures above $+150^\circ C$, and the dependencies for the experimental samples converge.

Test MC structures with different geometric parameters were fabricated using ion implantation. The results of the study on the influence of the geometric parameters of the MC topological structure, K_{p-n} and n , on the isolating properties of the p-n junction are presented in Figure 1. The temperature dependencies of the reverse current density for various test structures determine three regions.

(A) The high-density region of reverse current, labeled as "A," is formed by the dependencies of structures where the number of angles n is maximal ($n = 32$), and K_{p-n} is in the range of 800-1400 (#1, #2). In this case, extending the upper limit of the operating temperature range to values $T_{per} \geq 200^\circ C$ is unlikely. The areas of the isolating p-n junctions should be $A_{p-n} \leq 2 \times 10^{-5} cm^2$, which is more than three times smaller than the previously determined limit for the total area of the four contact pads of the MC.

(B) The range of intermediate values of J_{rev} labeled as "B" belongs to the dependencies of MC structures where the number of angles n is either 32 or 8, but K_{p-n} is in the range of $(500 \div 700) cm^{-1}$ (#4, #5, #7). Here, a realistic design for high temperatures is MC #7 with parameters $K_{p-n} = 500 cm^{-1}$ and $n = 8$ with a p-n junction area $A_{p-n} \leq 2 \times 10^{-4} cm^2$.

(C) The segment labeled as "C," for the ring-shaped structure MC #10 with $K_{p-n} = 500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, is characterized by a good agreement with the calculated dependence of $J_{rev}(T)$ for temperatures $T > 180^\circ\text{C}$. Differences at temperatures $T < 180^\circ\text{C}$ can be explained by the fact that the maximum limit value of S_0 , equal to $S_0 = 1 \times 10^4 \text{ cm/s}$, was chosen in the calculations for the dependence $J_{rev}(T)$. It is possible that in the actual MC, the value of S_0 may be 100 times smaller ⁴.

At the current level of integrated technology, it is fundamentally possible to reduce the area of the MC to a value of $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2$. This corresponds to a current density of $1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ A/cm}^{-2}$ and $I_{rev} = 1 \text{ }\mu\text{A}$.

It has been experimentally confirmed that the upper limit of the operating temperature range depends on the design parameters, such as the perimeter-to-area ratio of the isolating p-n junction, K_{p-n} , and the number of angles in the topological structure of the p-regions of the MC, n_{p-n} . Assuming that $A_{p-n} < 2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2$, $K_{p-n} = 500 \div 700$, and $n_{p-n} \leq 8$, the upper limit of the operating temperature range for IPT with an isolating p-n junction corresponds to values above $+200^\circ\text{C}$.

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